

Personalising and Revolutionising Language Learning Through Artificial Intelligent-Powered Applications among English Education students of Federal University Otuoke.

EKE, Regina Akudo, Ph.D¹ & AKUTEKWE, Chinenye Emilia²

¹ Department of Foundations, Arts and Social Sciences Education, Federal University, Otuoke.

²Department of Educational Foundations, Nnamdi Azikiwe University.

ekeregina@gmail.com.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17231416>

Abstract

This study investigated the use of Artificial Intelligent-Powered Applications in Personalising and Revolutionising Language Learning Among English Education Students of Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State. four research questions were answered and four hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. A descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consisted of 138 all year one and year two English Education Students at Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State. Purposive sampling technique was used to select the year one and two students while convenient sampling technique was used to select 58 English Education Students for data collection. The instrument used was researcher developed Checklist. The instrument was validated by three experts in measurements and evaluation. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha and coefficient indices of 0.88 was obtained. Data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions, while t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The study reveals that AI tools are essential in language teaching and learning because they enhance learners' engagement, provide personalised learning experiences, and improve language proficiency, particularly in speaking and writing. However, there are some limitations associated with their implementation, and their potential implications for the future of language learning, such as accessibility barriers, concerns about accuracy, cultural relevance, and bias in language instruction and ethical concerns around data privacy, security risks. Therefore, the review of findings aims at supporting educators, developers, and policymakers in fostering an AI-enriched learning environment that aligns with educational goals while addressing existing limitations.

Keywords: AI-Powered Applications, Language Learning, Personalising and Revolutionising,

Introduction

Language acquisition has experienced a significant evolution in recent decades, transitioning from conventional classroom teaching to digital and interactive platforms. However, the advent of artificial intelligence (AI) is radically transforming this domain, providing a more personalized, efficient, and engaging method for language learning. Gawate (2019) and Li (2020) demonstrated how artificial intelligence has altered the English learning environment for an interesting environment for immersive learning. The exploration of gamified environments enriched with AI is another avenue receiving attention. Yang et al. (2018) in his quest to investigate AI-powered gamified platforms, highlighted the importance of AI in personalizing game scenarios to improve learning outcomes. They claim that such platforms can make learning more personalized and engaging. AI tools such as Duolingo and Rosetta Stone effectively engage learners through

gamification and interactivity. These learning experiences not only sustain learner attention but also create personalized learning paths, maintain learners' interest and motivation, monitor their progress, and reward performance (Sajja et al., 2024). These learning opportunities make AI platforms more appealing to younger learners and self-directed study environments (Kristiawan, Bashar, & Pradana, 2024).

Traditional language learning frequently relies on standardized curriculum, textbooks, and strict teaching frameworks, failing to account for people's various learning styles, speeds, and preferences. In contrast, AI-driven language learning applications adapt dynamically to users' needs, providing real-time feedback, customized lesson plans, and interactive conversational simulations. AI platforms enable individualized learning experiences based on students' competency levels, learning styles, and areas for improvement (Stracke et al., 2022). Furthermore, AI-powered language learning programs are bridging geographical and economic divides by making high-quality education available to a worldwide audience. Learners from diverse backgrounds can now access customized language lessons at their own pace, fostering inclusivity and democratizing language acquisition (AbuSahyon et al., 2023). Using AI-driven language evaluation tools, educators can acquire profound insights into students' linguistic ability and develop focused solutions to overcome specific learning gaps (Kim et al., 2019).

AI-powered applications improve learning by utilizing technologies such as natural language processing (NLP), machine learning, and speech recognition. According to Kuddus (2022), AI-powered techniques such as machine learning, natural language processing, and intelligent tutoring have revolutionized English language teaching and learning by enabling adaptable, and immersive experiences that go beyond conventional teaching methods. These tools according to Arthars et al., (2019), may analyze vast datasets, discover patterns, and personalize information for each learner. English learning is made more thorough by logically integrating data such as visuals, speech, and text in intelligent devices. Artificial intelligence improves the effectiveness of English teaching. AI provides a realistic simulated conversation platform for English language teaching and learning (Wang, 2019). Furthermore, as AI continues to evolve, emerging innovations such as augmented reality (AR), virtual reality (VR), and real-time translation will further revolutionize the way languages are taught and learned.

One of the most difficult and anxiety-inducing language skills for English language learners is communicating in the target language. The development of artificial intelligence chatbots has created a promising platform for alleviating language learner anxiety. Artificial intelligence chatbots, such as Replica and Ellie, have demonstrated significant potential for reducing oral communication anxiety, a chronic impediment to optimal language acquisition outcomes and performance (Jegade, 2024; Tai, 2022). These tools create an immersive learning environment that allows learners to practice pronunciation, grammar, and vocabulary in a situation that mimics real-world speech, making the learning process more engaging and effective (Tolstykh & Oshchepkova, 2024). Furthermore, AI-powered applications use novel features such as chatbots, voice recognition, adaptive quizzes, and gamification to imitate real-life conversations and deliver an immersive language learning experience. AI technologies such as virtual teaching systems and interactive chatbots improve language acquisition by providing an immersive and interactive experience (AbuSahyon et al., 2023). According to Zhang et al. (2023), the use of chatbots as virtual teachers to improve language competency and communicative competence in the target language has increased significantly. These intelligent systems constantly learn from user interactions and

improve their teaching methods over time. The incorporation of AI also enables automatic language assessment, allowing learners to track their progress and identify areas for development.

Despite their various benefits, AI-powered language learning programs confront some obstacles and restrictions. These include data privacy problems, as Mohamed (2024) claimed that there are growing ethical worries regarding data privacy and the possibility of over-reliance on AI, which could overshadow crucial teacher-student interactions. Furthermore, there is a lack of emotional intelligence when compared to human instructors, as well as maintaining learner motivation, and ensuring the reliability of AI feedback, all of which are critical for effective language acquisition (Song & Song, 2023). Furthermore, AI technologies were trained on datasets with limited linguistic diversity, which may struggle to adapt non-standard accents, dialects, or regional language variances which makes it difficult to handle complex linguistic nuances such as idiomatic expressions and cultural context (Kristiawan, Bashar, & Pradana, 2024). This constraint may marginalize learners from minority language backgrounds and undermine inclusion.

Given AI's growing influence in education, this research investigates how AI-powered applications personalize and revolutionize language learning, their effectiveness in improving proficiency and retention, the challenges associated with their implementation, and their overall impact on learner engagement and motivation. By investigating these characteristics, this study hopes to provide useful insights into the future of AI-driven language teaching and its role in creating modern learning approaches.

Statement of the Problem

Language learning is a crucial ability in today's globalized society, yet many students struggle to achieve fluency and effective language acquisition owing to ineffective teaching techniques, a lack of personalization, and restricted access to high-quality language instruction. Conventional language learning methods frequently have a rigid structure that fails to suit individual learning styles, speeds, and skill levels. As a result, many students struggle with engagement, motivation, retention, and practical application of language abilities in real-life situations. The emergence of AI-powered language learning applications offers an innovative solution to these challenges by personalizing and revolutionizing language learning through adaptive and immersive experiences, as well as providing personalized learning experiences that adjust to each learner's unique pace and preferences. Therefore, this study tends to investigate the use of AI-Powered Applications in Personalising and Revolutionising Language Learning Among English Education Students of Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State.

Objectives of the study

The aim of this study is to;

1. examine the use of AI-driven features, such as natural language processing (NLP) and speech recognition, in revolutionizing language learning among male and female Students of English Education.
2. analyze the extent AI-powered applications improve accessibility in language learning among male and female students of English Education.
3. identify the challenges associated with AI-powered language learning applications among male and female students of English Education.
4. suggest possible solutions to the challenges of AI-powered language learning applications among male and female students of English Education.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent does AI-driven features, such as natural language processing (NLP) and speech recognition, in revolutionizing language learning among male and female students of English Education?
2. To what extent does AI-powered applications improve accessibility in language learning among male and female students of English Education?
3. What are the challenges associated with AI-powered language learning applications among male and female students of English Education?
4. What are the possible solutions to the challenges of AI-powered language learning applications among male and female students of English Educations.

Hypotheses

The following hypothesis were tested using t-test:

Hypothesis 1. The use of AI-powered applications does not significantly revolutionised language learning among male and female students of English Education.

Hypothesis 2. AI-powered applications does not significantly improve accessibility in language learning among male and female students of English Education.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference between the challenges male and female students of English Education experienced when using AI-powered language learning applications.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant difference between the suggestions offered by male and female English Education students as possible solutions to the challenges of using AI-powered language learning applications.

Research Method.

This research adopted a descriptive survey design. The population of the study consisted of 138 all year one and year two English Education Students at Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State. Purposive sampling technique was used to select the year one and two students since the school has only two levels of students offering English education. Convenient sampling technique was used to select 58 English Education Students for data collection because at the time this study was carried out, many students were yet to resume for the semester. A well-structured questionnaire was used for data collection. The instrument was validated by three experts in measurements and evaluation. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha and coefficient indices of 0.88 was obtained. The questionnaire was administered to the students and their responses were computed and used for the analysis. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while t-test was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance.

Table 1: Mean score and standard deviation of the extent AI-driven features, such as natural language processing (NLP) and speech recognition, revolutionise language learning among male and female students of English Education.

S/N	ITEMS	Male (N = 68)		Female (N = 70)		Mean Set	Remark
		Mean	St.D	Mean	St.D		
1.	I find NLP features in language learning applications helpful for improving my writing skills	3.07	0.97	3.10	0.97	3.09	Agree
2.	Speech recognition tools in AI-powered apps enhance my speaking and pronunciation skills	2.97	0.95	3.04	0.94	3.01	Agree
3.	AI tools offer more personalized feedback than traditional methods.	2.60	1.11	2.67	1.14	2.64	Agree
4.	I am more engaged when learning with AI-driven language applications.	2.56	1.11	2.61	1.12	2.59	Agree
5.	I believe AI features improve the overall effectiveness of my language learning experience.	3.10	0.98	3.11	1.00	3.11	Agree
Grand Mean Set & St.D		2.86	1.02	2.91	1.03	2.89	Agree

Table 1 presents the mean scores and standard deviations of male and female English Education students regarding the effect of AI-driven features, such as natural language processing (NLP) and speech recognition on language learning. With a grand mean of 2.89, both male and female students generally agree that AI features enhance writing skills, improve speaking and pronunciation, and contribute to more effective language learning experiences. This result suggests a positive effect of AI-driven tools in personalizing and revolutionizing language learning among the students.

Table 2: Mean score and standard deviation of the extent AI-powered applications improve accessibility in language learning among male and female students of English Education.

S/N	ITEMS	Male (N = 68)		Female (N = 70)		Mean Set	Remark
		Mean	St.D	Mean	St.D		
1.	AI-powered language apps are equally accessible to both male and female students.	3.03	0.91	3.06	0.98	3.04	High Extent
2.	I feel that AI language tools are accessible for students with different learning needs.	2.60	1.11	2.67	1.14	2.64	High Extent
3.	I can access AI language apps on my personal devices without difficulty.	3.10	0.95	3.14	0.94	3.12	High Extent
4.	AI-based tools make learning easier for students with limited language backgrounds.	2.60	1.11	2.67	1.14	2.64	High Extent
5.	I believe AI has reduced barriers to language learning for underrepresented groups.	2.51	1.11	2.60	1.12	2.56	High Extent
Grand Mean Set & St.D		2.77	1.04	2.83	1.06	2.80	High Extent

Table 2 displays the mean scores and standard deviations for male and female English Education students on the extent to which AI-powered applications improve accessibility in language learning. The grand mean of 2.80 indicates that students generally perceive AI tools as improving access to language materials and improve acquisition to a high extent. The findings suggest that AI-powered applications are viewed as effective in enhancing language learning accessibility for both male and female students.

Table 3: Mean score and standard deviation of the challenges male and female students of English Education experience when using AI-powered language learning applications.

S/N	ITEMS	Male (N = 68)		Female (N = 70)		Mean Set	Remark
		Mean	St.D	Mean	St.D		
1.	I face technical difficulties when using AI-powered language applications.	2.85	1.14	2.93	1.12	2.89	Agree
2.	Some AI applications require internet access, which limits my usage.	2.31	1.07	2.41	1.11	2.36	Agree
3.	I find it difficult to trust the accuracy of AI-generated corrections	2.94	0.96	2.97	1.01	2.96	Agree
4.	I lack sufficient training or orientation to use AI-based language tools effectively.	2.46	0.94	2.53	0.97	2.49	Agree
5.	AI tools sometimes misinterpret my spoken or written language.	3.38	0.85	3.41	0.84	3.40	Agree
Grand Mean Set & St.D		2.79	0.99	2.85	1.01	2.82	Agree

Table 3 shows the mean and standard deviation of male and female English Education students' responses on the challenges they experience when using AI-powered language learning applications. The grand mean of 2.82 indicates general agreement that challenges exist but are not overly severe. All item means are above 2.50, suggesting agreement that the challenges exist across various areas. Standard deviations between 0.84 and 1.14 reflect a moderate variation in student experiences.

Table 4: Mean score and standard deviation of the suggestions male and female students of English Education offer as possible solutions to the challenges of using AI-powered language learning applications.

S/N	ITEMS	Male (N = 68)		Female (N = 70)		Mean Set	Remark
		Mean	St.D	Mean	St.D		
1.	Institutions should invest in more reliable and accessible AI learning platforms.	3.38	0.81	3.41	0.84	3.40	Agree
2.	Providing orientation or training on AI tools would improve their use in language learning.	3.51	0.82	3.51	0.85	3.51	Agree
3.	AI language apps should be designed to work well even with poor internet connections.	3.19	0.90	3.21	0.88	3.20	Agree
4.	User feedback should be considered in improving the performance of AI tools.	3.40	0.83	3.40	0.84	3.40	Agree
5.	Local language support should be integrated into AI-powered apps to enhance accessibility	3.24	0.74	3.23	0.80	3.23	Agree
Grand Mean Set & St.D		3.34	0.82	3.35	0.84	3.35	Agree

Table 4 presents the mean and standard deviation of suggestions provided by male and female English Education students for addressing challenges in using AI-powered language learning applications. With a grand mean of 3.35, there is strong agreement across gender groups on proposed solutions. Students particularly support training, improved accessibility, and consideration of user feedback.

Table 5: T-test analysis showing that the use of AI-powered applications does not significantly revolutionise language learning among male and female students of English Education.

Gender	N	SD	df	T	p	Decision
Male	68	2.86	136	-0.277	0.782	Ho₁ Retained
Female	70	2.91	1.00			p > 0.05

Table 5 presents the results of a T-test analysis to determine whether a significant difference exists between male and female English Education students regarding the effect of AI-driven features such as natural language processing (NLP) and speech recognition on the personalization and transformation of language learning. The t-score of -0.277 and p-value of 0.782 indicate that there is no statistically significant difference between the responses of male students (mean = 2.86, SD =

0.99) and female students (mean = 2.91, SD = 1.00), since the p-value is greater than the 0.05 significance level. Therefore, the null hypothesis (Ho1) is retained, implying that both male and female students experience AI-driven language learning in a similar way.

Table 6: T-test analysis of significant difference in the extent to which AI-powered applications improve accessibility in language learning among male and female English Education students.

Gender	N	Mean	SD	df	T	p	Decision
Male	68	2.77	1.01	136	-0.334	0.739	Ho1 Retained
Female	70	2.82	1.03				p > 0.05

Table 6 presents the results of a T-test analysis to examine whether a significant difference exists between male and female English Education students in the extent to which AI-powered applications improve accessibility in language learning. The t-score of -0.334 and p-value of 0.739 indicate that there is no statistically significant difference between the responses of male students (mean = 2.77, SD = 1.01) and female students (mean = 2.82, SD = 1.03), as the p-value is greater than the 0.05 significance level. Therefore, the null hypothesis (Ho1) is retained, suggesting that both male and female students experience similar levels of accessibility through AI-powered language learning applications.

Table 7: T-test analysis of significant difference between the challenges male and female students of English Education experienced when using AI-powered language learning applications.

Gender	N	Mean	SD	df	T	p	Decision
Male	68	2.79	0.93	136	-0.393	0.695	Ho1 Retained
Female	70	2.85	0.96				p > 0.05

Table 7 presents the results of a T-test analysis to determine if there is a significant difference between the perceptions of male and female English Education students regarding the challenges experienced when using AI-powered language learning applications. The t-value of -0.393 and the p-value of 0.695 indicate no statistically significant difference between the perceptions of male students (mean = 2.79, SD = 0.93) and female students (mean = 2.85, SD = 0.96), as the p-value is greater than the 0.05 significance level. Therefore, the null hypothesis is retained, implying that both male and female students share similar views on the challenges associated with using AI-powered language learning tools.

Table 8: T-test analysis of significant difference between the suggestions offered by male and female students of English Education as possible solutions to the challenges of using AI-powered language learning applications.

Gender	N	SD	df	T	p	Decision	
Male	68	3.34	0.78	136	-0.075	0.940	Ho1 Retained
Female	70	3.35	0.81				p > 0.05

Table 8 presents the results of a T-test analysis to determine whether there is a significant difference between the perceptions of male and female English Education students regarding the suggestions offered as solutions to the challenges of using AI-powered language learning applications. The t-value of -0.075 and the p-value of 0.940 show that there is no statistically significant difference between the mean ratings of male students (mean = 3.34, SD = 0.78) and female students (mean = 3.35, SD = 0.81), since the p-value is greater than the 0.05 significance level. Therefore, the null hypothesis is retained, indicating that both genders share similar suggestions on addressing the challenges of AI in language learning.

Discussion and Findings.

The findings from Table 1 reveal that both male and female English Education students have a positive outlook on the role of AI-driven features, such as natural language processing (NLP) and speech recognition, in enhancing language learning. The students recognize the benefits of these technologies in improving their writing, speaking, and overall language skills. Supporting this, Table 5 shows that there is no statistically significant difference between male and female students in how they experience these AI-driven tools. This confirms the null hypothesis (Ho1), indicating that both genders perceive the impact of AI on language learning similarly. Together, these results highlight a shared appreciation among students for the personalization and transformation AI brings to language education. These results align with literature emphasizing AI's transformative role in education. Kuddus (2022) noted that AI powered applications such as machine learning and intelligent tutoring systems, have revolutionized English Language Teaching through adaptive and immersive learning. Arthars et al. (2019) also highlight how AI customizes content by analyzing learning patterns, an advantage likely reflected in students' favorable perceptions of AI-supported, personalized language learning.

The findings from Table 2 indicate that both male and female English Education students perceive AI-powered applications as significantly enhancing accessibility in language learning, as evidenced by the positive grand mean of 2.80. This suggests that students broadly agree on the effectiveness of AI tools in making language learning more accessible and enhances language acquisition. Further supporting this, the t test analysis in Table 6 shows no statistically significant difference between male and female students' responses. This confirms the null hypothesis (Ho2) and suggests that both genders share a similar recognition of AI's important role in promoting accessible language education. These findings are supported by Wei (2023), who highlights that AI-mediated instruction improves English learning outcomes, self-regulated learning, and L2 motivation benefits also recognized by students in this study. Similarly, Kim et al. (2025) found that students value AI for its multifaceted support in academic writing, including emotional and motivational aspects. These insights reflect the students' appreciation of AI not only as a tool for access but also as a means to enhance engagement, personalization, and learning outcomes.

The findings from Table 3 indicate that both male and female English Education students acknowledge the presence of challenges when using AI-powered language learning applications, suggesting moderate concern. The agreement across items implies that while students do face challenges, these are not perceived as highly severe. Table 7 confirms no significant gender difference in these perceptions, indicating shared experiences of challenges across both groups. These results align with Gawate, (2019) and Li, (2020) who reported improved speaking performance through AI tools like Google Assistant but also noted practical challenges such as connectivity and accessibility issues. Similarly, Chinonso, Theresa, and Aduke (2023) found that while learners appreciated the personalization and usefulness of AI technologies, educators highlighted limitations including ethical concerns and technological compatibility. Together, these studies support the current finding that although AI tools are valued in language learning, users both students and teachers, face notable but manageable challenges in their application.

The findings from Table 4 reveal strong agreement among both male and female English Education students on practical suggestions for addressing challenges in using AI-powered language learning tools, including training, enhanced accessibility, and incorporating user feedback. The T-test results in Table 8 show no significant gender differences in these suggestions, indicating shared perspectives across both groups. These findings are supported by Kovalenko and Baranivska (2024), who emphasized the importance of infrastructural development, teacher training, and alignment with curriculum goals for effective AI integration. Their study also reinforces the students' call for inclusive and personalized learning approaches, while cautioning about ethical and privacy concerns. Together, this affirms that students recognize not only the potential of AI but also the practical steps needed to ensure its effective and equitable use in language education.

Conclusion

This study reveals that AI-driven features such as natural language processing (NLP) and speech recognition positively impact in the personalization and effectiveness of language learning among English Education students. Both male and female students generally agree on the benefits of these AI tools in improving writing, speaking, and overall language proficiency.

Additionally, AI-powered applications are perceived as significantly enhancing accessibility and inclusivity in language learning for all students, regardless of gender. The absence of significant differences between male and female students' responses further underscores a shared positive experience and acceptance of AI technologies in language education.

Students also acknowledged the existence of challenges, although these were not perceived as overly severe. Commonly identified challenges include connectivity, accessibility, and technical limitations. Despite these issues, students offered strong and consistent suggestions for improvement, especially emphasizing the need for user training, improved infrastructure, and feedback-driven app development.

Across all areas of investigation, including perceptions, challenges, and proposed solutions, there were no statistically significant differences between male and female students. This uniformity suggests that both genders experience and evaluate AI-powered language learning applications in similar ways.

Recommendations.

1. Teachers should be involved in the selection and integration of AI tools to ensure alignment with curriculum goals and to mitigate resistance to technology adoption.
2. AI-powered tools should be designed to cater to diverse learning needs, cultural backgrounds, and language proficiencies to ensure equitable access for all learners.

3. Institutions should provide training sessions and orientation programs for students and teachers to maximize the effective use of AI-driven language tools.
4. Educational institutions and developers should work on enhancing internet connectivity and ensuring stable access to AI applications, especially in resource-limited settings.
5. Developers and institutions must establish clear guidelines on data privacy, user consent, and ethical use of AI to foster trust and ensure responsible application in education.

Reference

- AbuSahyon, A. S. A. E., Alzyoud, A., Alshorman, O., & Al-Absi, B. (2023). AI-driven Technology and Chatbots as Tools for Enhancing English Language Learning in the Context of Second Language Acquisition: A Review Study. *International Journal of Membrane Science and Technology*, 10(1), 1209-1223. <https://doi.org/10.15379/ijmst.v10i1.2829>
- Arthars, N., Dollinger, M., Vigentini, L., Liu, D. Y.-T., Kondo, E., & King, D. M. (2019). Empowering Teachers to Personalize Learning Support: Case Studies of Teachers' Experiences Adopting a Student-and Teacher-Centered Learning Analytics Platform at Three Australian Universities. *Utilizing Learning Analytics to Support Study Success*, 223–248.
- Chinonso, O., Theresa, A., & Aduke, T. (2023). ChatGPT For Teaching, Learning and Research: Prospects and Challenges. *Global Academic Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 5(2), 33-40. doi:10.36348/gajhss.2023.v05i02.001
- Gawate, S. (2019). Artificial Intelligence (AI) Based Instructional Programs in Teaching-Learning of English Language. *International Journal of English Language, Literature and Translation Studies (IJELR)*, 6(6). 64-69.
- Jegede, O. O. (2024). Artificial intelligence and English language learning: Exploring the roles of AI-driven tools in personalizing learning and providing instant feedback. *Universal Library of Languages and Literatures*, 1 (2), 6-19. <https://doi.org/10.70315/uloap.ulli.2024.0102002>
- Kaur, D. J., & Gill, N. S. (2019). *Artificial Intelligence and Deep Learning for Decision Makers: A Growth Hacker's Guide to Cutting Edge Technologies*. BPB Publications.
- Kim, N.-Y., Cha, Y., & Kim, H.-S. (2019). Future English learning: Chatbots and artificial intelligence. *Multimedia-Assisted Language Learning*, 22(3), 32-53.
- Kuddus, K. (2022). Artificial intelligence in language learning: Practices and prospects. *Advanced Analytics and Deep Learning Models*, 1–17.
- Kristiawan, D., Y., Bashar, K., & Pradana, D. A. (2024). Artificial intelligence in English language learning: A systematic review of ai tools, applications, and pedagogical outcomes. *The Art of Teaching English as a Foreign Language (TATEFL)*, 5(2), 207-218. <https://doi.org/10.36663/tatefl.v5i2.912>
- Mohamed, M. S. P. (2024). Exploring ethical dimensions of AI-enhanced language education: A literature perspective. *Technology in Language Teaching & Learning*, 6(3), 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.29140/tltl.v6n3.1813>
- Sajja, R., Sermet, Y., Cikmaz, M., Cwiertny, D., & Demir, I. (2024). Artificial intelligence enabled intelligent assistant for personalized and adaptive learning in higher education. *Information*, 15(10), p. 596. <https://doi.org/10.3390/info15100596>

- Song, C., & Song, Y. (2023). Enhancing academic writing skills and motivation: assessing the efficacy of ChatGPT in AI-assisted language learning for EFL students. *Frontiers in Psychology*, p.14. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1260843>
- Stracke, C. M., Burgos, D., Santos-Hermosa, G., Bozkurt, A., Sharma, R. C., Swiatek Cassafieres, C., Dos Santos, A. I., Mason, J., Ossiannilsson, E., & Shon, J. G. (2022). Responding to the initial challenge of the COVID-19 pandemic: Analysis of international responses and impact in school and higher education. *Sustainability*, 14(3), p.1876.
- Tai T. Y. (2022) Effects of intelligent personal assistants on EFL learners' oral proficiency outside the classroom. *Computer Assisted Language learning*, 37(5-6), 1281-1310.
- Tolstykh, O. M., & Oshchepkova, T. (2024). Beyond ChatGPT: roles that artificial intelligence tools can play in an English language classroom. *Discover Artificial Intelligence*, 4(1), p.60. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s44163-024-00158-9>
- Wang, R. (2019). Research on Artificial Intelligence Promoting English Learning Change. *3rd International Conference on Economics and Management, Education, Humanities and Social Sciences*. China. doi:10.2991/emehss-19.2019.79
- Yang, D., Sinha, T., Adamson, D., & Rosé, C. P. (2018). Turn on, tune in, drop out: Anticipating student dropouts in Massive Open Online Courses. *Proceedings of the 2013 NIPS Data-driven education workshop*, 11(15), 1-14.
- Zhang R., Zou D, Cheng G. (2023) A review of chatbot-assisted learning: Pedagogical approaches, implementations, factors leading to effectiveness, theories, and future directions. *Interactive learning Environments*, 1-29. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10494820>.